

Pleiotropic Benefits of Proton Pump Inhibitors Beyond Gastric Acid Control

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ABSTRACT

Proton pump inhibitors are recommended for the treatment of peptic acid disorders like duodenal ulcer, gastric ulcer, oesophageal reflux disorders. They are also used for NSAID induced and for ischemia reperfusion related gastrointestinal injuries. In addition to the anti secretory effect, PPIs have been found to have antioxidant, anti inflammatory and antidiabetic properties They are also used as an adjunct in the treatment and prevention of chemoresistant tumors. Their anti inflammatory property is attributed to the inhibition of expression of adhesion molecules on the neutrophils, monocytes and the endothelial cells. In addition, decreased release of pro inflammatory mediators and up regulation of heme oxygenase –1 also contribute to this action. Keap-1/Nrf-2 and MAP kinases have role to play in the upregulation of enzyme heme oxygenase-1 by PPIs. Inhibition of oxidative burst by neutrophils and impaired neutrophil migration also help in anti inflammatory actions of PPIs. Antioxidant effect of PPIs is attributed to the scavenging of reactive oxygen species, replenishment of protective sulfhydryl molecule in the gastric mucosa and the induction of heme oxygenase-1. Recently anti diabetic properties of PPIs have been highlighted. PPIs mediate glucose lowering effect by increased gastrin levels, increased beta cell neogenesis and mass, increased insulin secretion. Inhibition of ghrelin, activation of central CCK-B receptors and GLP-1 activation from intestinal L cells also contribute to this effect. The PPIs are used as an adjunct treatment for malignancy and also to prevent chemoresistance. The mechanism responsible for this effect of PPIs on the malignant cells is through inhibition of V-ATPases and change in physiological pH which makes them susceptible for apoptosis and self digestion. This also results in to the increased drug retention in the alkaline pH of malignant cells.

Keywords:

INTRODUCTION

Proton pump inhibitors [PPIs] are the substituted benzimidazoles, which inhibit gastric parietal cell P type H⁺K⁺ATPase proton pumps and block the gastric acid secretion¹. PPIs are the weak bases which after absorption, accumulate in the parietal cell acidic environment. They are the pro drugs which get activated after protonation of their pyridine and benzimidazole nitrogen in to active tetracyclic sulfenamide which bind to proton pumps and inhibit them². PPIs are the most effective anti secretory agents recommended for the treatment of acid peptic disorders like duodenal ulcer, gastric ulcer, gastro esophageal reflux disorders[GERDs], NSAID induced gastric mucosal injury and Helicobacter pylori infection²⁻¹⁰. PPI protect the bowel mucosa against indomethacin and ischemia induced injury. This effect is unrelated to the acid suppressive effect of PPI and is attributed to the anti inflammatory property of PPI^{9,10}. In addition to anti inflammatory property, PPIs have been proved to have anti diabetic¹¹, antioxidant¹², anti malignancy¹³ and antimicrobial actions¹⁴.

Effect of PPI on the glycemic control in diabetes mellitus [DM]

PPIs bind to proton pumps irreversibly and block the gastric acid secretion. They indirectly elevate serum gastrin levels via a negative feedback mechanism¹⁵⁻²⁰. Gastrin is a linear peptide hormone secreted by gastric pyloric antrum G cells, in which biologically active gastrin 17 and gastrin 34 are formed^{15,21}. Gastrin acts as a growth factor and stimulates parietal cell proliferation^{22,23}. It is also known to stimulate beta cell neogenesis in pancreatic ductal complex²⁴, replicate pancreatic beta cells and improves glucose homeostasis²³. Increased gastrin levels arising out of negative feedback mechanism improve glycemic control in diabetics probably by augmenting beta cell mass and insulin release²⁵. Most of the clinical studies have shown significant control of hyperglycemia in type 2 DM^{11,26-31}. But there are few studies which observed, negative results regarding the effect of PPIs on glycemic control^{32,33}. In some of the clinical studies where glycemic control was improved by PPIs²⁶⁻³¹, it appeared that higher the levels of blood sugar and HbA1c, better was the

control²⁷. The observed negative effect of PPI on blood sugar control was correlated to the already good controlled blood sugar and of HbA1c^{32,33}. It was observed that the elevated gastrin level by PPI is not always needed for good glycemic control³⁰. This suggests the possibility of some other mechanisms other than increased gastrin levels and increased beta cell mass for glycemic control. Other suggested possible mechanism is the interrelation of gastrin with ghrelin which has an important role to play in appetite regulation and energy homeostasis. Gastrin and ghrelin have negative correlation in human beings, thereby increased gastrin and decreased ghrelin result in to reduced appetite and good glucose control³⁴. Cholecystokinin B [CCK-B] receptors are present in the brain mainly in the hypothalamic region^{35,36}. Cholecystokinin [CCK] is secreted from the duodenum in response to food. CCK acts on CCK-B receptors in the brain and suppresses satiety centre and is anorexigenic. Diffusion of gastrin in the brain is limited by blood brain barrier³⁷. But either peptide or peptide fragments might enter in to the brain through circum ventricular organs³⁸. Circulating gastrin can stimulate CCK-B receptors in the area postrema neurons which project to the nucleus tractus solitaries [NTS] and suppresses the appetite³⁹. Thus it is possible that increase in serum gastrin by PPIs directly inhibits appetite through central nervous system and also by acting indirectly on the brain stem via vagal nerve³⁹. Now it is revealed that gastrin stimulates Glucagon like peptide-1 [GLP-1] secretion from the L cells in the small intestine⁴⁰. GLP-1 induces both beta cell replication with mitogens and neogenesis of beta cells from the ductal cells. GLP-1 stimulates insulin release, inhibits glucagon secretion, suppresses the appetite by central effect and decreases gastro intestinal motility^{41,42}. This all help to control hyperglycemia. Clinical studies have proved the synergistic effect of PPI like lansoprazole either with dipeptidyl peptidase-4 [DPP-4] inhibitors like sitagliptin which blocks the degradation of GLP-1 and increases its levels or with GLP-1 analogue like liraglutide⁴³⁻⁴⁵. Thus, the various mechanisms for the effect of PPI on glycemic control are- increased gastrin release, enhanced beta cell mass and insulin release, inhibition of ghrelin, action on CCK-B receptors centrally and on vagus nerve and stimulation of GLP-1. The combination of GLP-1 and gastrin may protect from the onset or the progression of type I DM by an immune regulatory effect. It may be possible that PPI might be having other unknown mechanisms also for glycemic control which needs to be explored by further studies.

Antioxidant property of PPI

Antioxidant property of PPI is mediated by direct scavenging of reactive oxygen species [ROS] and by up regulation of stress inducible cytoprotective enzyme heme oxygenase-1 [HO-1] in endothelial and epithelial cells. In addition PPI increase mucosal levels of glutathione and other antioxidants¹². HO-1 induction is related to the anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and cytoprotective action. This enzyme catalyses heme degradation and generate antioxidant bilirubin and cytoprotective carbon monoxide [CO]¹². HO-1 is inducible by stimuli like oxidative stress,

ischemia reperfusion injury, bacterial liposaccharides, cytokines, nitric oxide, heat shock, ultraviolet radiation and also by its substrate heme. Enzyme HO-1 while catalyzing heme degradation generate ferrous iron [Fe⁺⁺]. Release of Fe⁺⁺ triggers the synthesis of ferritin which sequesters free iron, slows down iron dependent redox [Fenton] reaction and acts as an antioxidant^{46,47}. CO has been shown to have antioxidant, anti apoptotic, anti-inflammatory, antiproliferative and bronchodilator properties^{48,49}. Omeprazole and other PPI get converted in to tetracyclic sulfenamide in gastric parietal cell acidic PH which provide sulfhydryl compounds to gastric mucosa and function as antioxidant. In rats, indomethacin induced gastric mucosal injury and glutathione depletion was prevented by pre treatment with esomeprazole^{50,51}. PPIs like lansoprazole and omeprazole have been proved to have direct scavenging action against ROS which were generated during reaction with transition metals or by copper induced oxidation of low density lipoproteins [LDL]⁵²⁻⁵⁴. In inflammatory conditions like peptic ulcer disease, oxidative stress causes tissue damage. Oxidant injuries are mediated by the production of toxic agents like hypochlorous acid by phagocytes and by transition metals like iron and copper present in various tissues^{55,56}. In vitro studies omeprazole was found to prevent the hypochlorous acid induced oxidation of beta carotene and was also observed to inhibit oxidation of deoxyribose sugar, mediated by iron and copper⁵⁶. Several signaling molecules like mitogen activated protein kinases [MAPK] and transcriptional regulators like activator protein-1, NF-E2 related factor- 2 [Nrf-2], hypoxia-inducible factor-1 and Bach-1 regulate the ho-1 gene⁵⁷⁻⁶⁰. Lansoprazole was observed to upregulate HO-1 expression by activation, phosphorylation, nuclear translocation of Nrf-2 along with dissection of oxidized Kelch like ECH dissociating protein- 1 [Keap- 1]⁶¹. By production of proinflammatory cytokines like TNF alpha and interleukin 1-B [IL-1B], neutrophils, macrophages and mononuclear cells play an important role in gastrointestinal inflammation⁶². In addition to acid suppression, PPI like lansoprazole has been observed to reduce the inflammation and oxidative stress resulting in to amelioration of mucosal injuries in the esophagus⁶³⁻⁶⁵, stomach⁶⁶, intestines^{9,10,67} and lungs⁶⁸. PPI were also found to block NADPH dependent ROS formation⁶⁹.

Anti inflammatory property of PPI

This property of PPI is attributed to Prevention of expression of adhesion molecules on polymorphonuclear leucocytes and on endothelial cells. Down regulation of proinflammatory cytokines like TNF alpha and interleukin [IL].1-B and IL-6. Upregulation of stress inducible protein HO-1. Helicobacter pylori and NSAIDs are known to induce gastric mucosal injury by activating polymorphonuclear leucocytes which initially adhere to the venules and then migrate in to the interstitium and induce inflammation⁷⁰⁻⁷⁴. Certain adhesion molecules expressed on the surface of leucocytes facilitate their adhesion to endothelial cells^{75,76}. These are CD 11/CD 18 integrin family composed of alpha subunit [CD 11 a-c] and beta-2 subunit of CD 18^{75,77,78}. Adhesion and trans

endothelial migration of leucocytes is facilitated by these molecules. Similarly, adhesion molecules are also expressed on activated endothelial cells which help for the adhesion of leucocytes and mononuclear cells to the endothelial cells. These are intercellular adhesion molecule-1 [ICAM-1] and vascular adhesion molecule -1 [VCAM-1]. ICAM-1 acts as ligand for CD 11/CD 18 on leucocytes⁷⁷ and VCAM-1 for very late activation antigen-4 [VLA-4] on mononuclear cells⁷⁹. In experimental studies surface expression of CD 11 and CD 18 on leucocytes and their adhesion to endothelial cells was reduced by lansoprazole and omeprazole. It is possible that PPI act either on signal transduction pathway or translocation and conformational changes of CD 11/CD 18 complex⁸⁰. Activation of transcription factor, nuclear factor kappa B and synthesis of mRNA is required for the expression of ICAM-1 and VCAM-1 on the endothelial cells. Possibly PPI act on signal transduction of protein synthesis of these adhesion molecules- ICAM -1 and VCAM-1^{81,82}. PPI reduced the migration of neutrophils⁸³. Neutrophils treated with omeprazole showed inhibited oxidative burst and also had impaired ability of phagocytosis⁸⁴. Inhibition of vacuolar type[V type] H⁺ ATPase located on the leucocytes by PPI may be responsible for reduced superoxide production, inhibition of chemotaxis and degranulation⁸¹. PPI are proved to block V-ATPases on the leucocytes and on the endothelial cells⁸⁵⁻⁸⁷. Inhibition of these V-ATPases on the leucocytes and endothelial cells prevent the expression of their adhesion molecules like CD 11/CD 18 on leucocytes and ICAM-1 and VCAM -1 on endothelial cells^{80,88-91}. This prevents ROS release and the adhesion of leucocytes to the endothelial cells resulting in to the prevention and progression of inflammation. In human studies PPIs like omeprazole and lansoprazole were found to decrease the number of peripheral mononuclear cells that express ICAM-1⁹². PPI may exert anti-inflammatory activity by inhibiting the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines which recruit the inflammatory cells at the site of inflammation^{88,93}. PPIs have been shown to decrease the levels of IL-6, IL-8 and TNF alpha⁸⁹. Mammalian enzyme heme oxygenase [HO] has three isoenzymes. HO-1 is one of them, which is a stress responsive protein. HO-1 plays an important role in the anti inflammatory and antioxidant effect of PPI¹². HO-1 catalyses heme degradation, generates bilirubin having antioxidant property and CO with cytoprotective property. It was found that lansoprazole and omeprazole both induce the expression of HO-1 mRNA and protein in human endothelial cells and gastric cell lines. Thus PPI regulate HO-1 expression and its up-regulation¹². Keap-1 and Nrf-2 have a role to play in the lansoprazole induced upregulation of HO-1. Nrf-2 is a key regulator of adaptive response to oxidative stress⁹⁴⁻⁹⁷ and of the transcriptional activation of ho-1 gene⁹⁸. Common mechanism involve for the stress response element [StRE]/Nrf-2 transcription pathway for the gene regulation in response to various HO-1 inducers. Lansoprazole mediated upregulation of HO-1 was Nrf-2 dependent and was also due to increased binding of Nrf-2 to StREs⁹⁹. MAP kinases have important role in upregulation of HO-1 induced by lansoprazole. HO-1

induction can take place by multiple protein kinase pathways such as MAP kinase, protein kinase C and p38 MAP kinase. Experimental studies indicated that HO-1 upregulation by lansoprazole was partly mediated by ERK pathway^{100,101}. Thus lansoprazole exerts anti-inflammatory effect through HO-1 upregulation. Phosphorylation of ERK, Nrf-2 activation, nuclear translocation of Nrf-2 and oxidation of Keap-1 are involved in the lansoprazole induced HO-1 upregulation. Nuclear translocation of Nrf-2 and StRE binding of Nrf-2 upregulate HO-1 mRNA leading to upregulation of HO-1 protein reuptake resulting in to anti inflammatory effect⁹⁹. The potential benefits of anti inflammatory action of PPI may be considered in treating inflammatory diseases, intestinal or extra intestinal, unrelated to acid-pepsin etiology. Eosinophilic esophagitis was successfully treated by PPIs¹⁰² and now PPIs are recommended for the treatment of eosinophilic esophagitis¹⁰³⁻¹⁰⁵. Effect of esomeprazole was studied in lung inflammation and fibrosis. It was observed that along with anti inflammatory and antioxidant effect as described earlier, it was also suggested to have anti fibrotic, anti proliferative and anti apoptotic effect. Anti fibrotic effect was thought to be mediated by upregulation of HO-1^{12,106}, down regulation of DDAAH activity and down regulation of inducible NOS[iNOS]^{107,108}. The other contributing factors for this effect are down regulation of TGF -beta machinery [TGF betaR1 and TGF beta R2]and also down regulation of MMPs and fibronectin¹⁰⁹. Upregulation of HO-1 and increased CO levels were also responsible for anti proliferative and anti apoptotic actions of PPI^{12,106}. Anti apoptotic effect was also attributed to the down regulation of p53 and up regulation of chitinase-3 like -1[CHI 3L1]¹⁰⁹.

Role of PPI in the treatment of malignancy

Modification of cellular pH by the action of PPI on vacuolar H⁺ATPases [V-ATPases] of the malignant cells has been proposed modality to treat malignancy and to prevent the chemoresistance. V-ATPases are the large multi unit proton pumps distributed within the plasma membrane and membranes of some organelles such as lysosomes, endosomes and secretory vesicles of many cells including tumor cells¹¹⁰. Their function includes acidification of lysosome, endosome and phagosome compartments and also extracellular environment of the cell and to keep cytosolic pH around 7^{111,112}. This pH regulation is essential for regulation of physiological functions of the cells¹¹¹⁻¹¹³. It is now confirmed that V-ATPase is responsible for carcinogenesis, growth, progression, invasion and metastasis of cancer. Hence inhibition of V-ATPase becomes an important target for cancer chemotherapy¹¹⁴. Agents altering tumor pH homeostasis exert antitumor activity by inhibiting tumor growth, its metastasis and by reverting chemoresistance¹¹⁵⁻¹¹⁸. Mammalian V-ATPase is composed of V1 and Vo domain.^{113, 119} V1 governs ATP hydrolysis and Vo by trans membrane transport of protons, keeps extracellular milieu and lysosomal pH acidic and intracellular cytosolic pH alkaline around 7¹¹¹⁻¹¹³. In the tumor cells the energy generation shifts from oxidative phosphorylation to aerobic glycolysis known as Warburg effect, creating

intracellular acidosis which is not conducive for the cell survival and can result in to self digestion of the cell^{120,121}. Hence for their survival and for protection from self digestion and apoptosis, protons need to get extruded to maintain cytosolic pH between neutral to alkaline¹²¹⁻¹²³. V-ATPase plays a major role to maintain this pH.¹²⁴ Suppression of this proton extrusion by inhibition of V-ATPase makes tumor cell more susceptible to cell death and apoptosis, as was found in various human cancer cell lines like liver cancer,¹²⁵ breast cancer¹²⁶, gastric cancer¹²⁷ and B cell hybridoma cells^{128,129}. Inhibition of V-ATPase will decrease cytosolic pH and increase lysosomal pH affecting lysosomal function and resulting in to apoptosis through lysosomal mediation. This can be also due to increased lysosomal pH and permeability, triggering the release of cathepsin D and activation of caspase¹²⁷. Inhibition of V-ATPase suppresses anti apoptotic Bcl-2 and Bcl-L and facilitate caspase dependent apoptotic pathway¹³⁰. Inhibition of V-ATPase initiates apoptosis due to accumulation of reactive oxygen species[ROS]^{131,129}. V-ATPase are known to regulate tumor associated m-TOR [mammalian target of rapamycin]¹³², Notch^{133,134} or Wnt^{135,136}. V-ATPase is required for the activation of Notch which is common hallmark of increasing numbers of cancers^{137,138}. The invasive nature of malignancy is correlated with highly active V-ATPase causing activation of proteases and breaking down of the extracellular matrix. Tumors like melanoma¹³⁹ pancreatic cancer¹⁴⁰ and breast cancer^{141,142} are correlated with this phenomenon. Extracellular acidic pH of malignant cells along with activated proteases also activate cathepsin, metalloproteases and gelatinase, which in turn activate other proteases and matrix metalloproteases causing invasion¹⁴³⁻¹⁴⁵. The plasma membrane V-ATPase gets recruited at the proceeding edge of the cancer cells which interacts with F-actin to produce acidic microenvironment at the edge. Intracellular V-ATPase also helps in invasion and metastasis by shifting the proteases containing secretory vesicles to the cell surface to be exocytosed. Acquired multi drug resistance [MDR] limits the therapeutic potential resulting in to relapse. MDR is correlated with the family of ATP binding cassette [ABC] proteins –P glycoprotein and V-ATPase. Inhibition of V-ATPase directly suppresses the tumor cells and sensitize them to chemotherapy and reverses the chemoresistance¹⁴⁶. It is documented that pretreatment with PPI like omeprazole sensitize the tumor cells for cisplatin, 5-fluorouracil and vinblastin along with enhanced cytosolic retention of these drugs¹⁴⁷. The drugs which are known to change tumor pH are prone to be having antitumor effect by reverting drug resistance and inhibiting tumor growth and metastatic progression. Hence these have become suitable therapeutic adjuncts. Several studies have shown that PPI like omeprazole, esomeprazole and pantoprazole have anti neoplastic activity against human haemopoietic and solid tumors. PPI being pro drugs get activated in tumor cell acidic pH. Treatment with PPI changes tumor pH gradient leading to drug retention and traffick of acidic vesicles in human melanoma and gastric carcinoma. PPI have shown to decrease chemoresistance in

the drug resistant tumors and can induce direct tumor cell killing^{13,129}. Hence PPI have been proposed as valid and feasible approach with relatively low toxicity and potential selectivity for tumor cells. Chemically modified omeprazole containing NAC molecule [NACO] to increase its bioavailability has been shown to induce apoptosis in human melanoma^{148,149}. Thus inhibition of V-ATPases of malignant cells by PPI inhibited tumor growth and proved to revert the chemoresistance.

Effects of PPI on gut microflora

Normally gastric acid kills the ingested microbials and limits their transmission to the intestines. By blocking gastric acid secretion, PPI increase the concentration of organisms in the stomach, oral cavity and upper small intestine and in the lungs through acid reflux^{150,151}. But PPIs are also known to act on bacterial cell membrane H⁺ATPase and block them. They inhibit their growth and even can kill some of the organisms like *Helicobacter pylori*, streptococci, lactobacilli, candida albicans and *s cerevisiae*^{14,151,152}. Thus, effect of PPI on organisms could be pro inflammatory in some parts of the gut and anti inflammatory in others. Lansoprazole when tried on rhinovirus infected human tracheal epithelial cell culture, was found to inhibit this infection by reducing ICAM-1 and by reducing the endogenous production of IL-1 beta and also by blocking the entry of rhinovirus RNA in to endosomes⁸⁹. Lansoprazole was found to have intracellular activity against *m. tuberculosis*. Lansoprazole kills the tubercular bacilli by targeting their cytochrome bc1 complex by intracellular sulfoxide reduction of lansoprazole to lansoprazole sulfide. This novel class of cytochrome bc1 inhibitor is highly active against drug resistant clinical isolates and spares the human H⁺K⁺ATPase. This provides an excellent opportunity for targeting the major pathogen *M. tuberculosis*.

CONCLUSION

PPIs along with being gastric acid anti secretory drug have got pleiotropic benefits beyond acid control. These include anti inflammatory, antioxidant, and antidiabetic. They also have role to play as an adjunct in the treatment of neoplastic disorders and in the prevention of chemoresistance. PPIs have been used to treat tumors of breast, liver, stomach and melanomas. Recently their role as an antidiabetic is very much highlighted by many studies conducted on type 2 DM patients, which showed positive results, where pretreatment levels of blood sugar and of HbA1c were high and uncontrolled. For this anti diabetic effect various mechanisms have been put forth. Although PPIs promise to be potential anti diabetics, a prospective, long term, randomized, double blind and placebo controlled studies are required to confirm this effect in a large number of patients with type 2 DM.

REFERENCES

1. Shin J, Sachs G. Pharmacology of Proton Pump Inhibitors. *Curr Gastroenterol Rep*. 2008; 10(6): 528–534.

2. Shi S, Klotz U. Proton pump inhibitors: an update of their clinical use and pharmacokinetics. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol.* 2008; 64(10): 935-51.
3. Hongo M, Kinoshita Y, Miwa H, Ashida K. The demographic characteristics and health-related quality of life in a large cohort of reflux esophagitis patients in Japan with reference to the effect of lansoprazole: the REQUEST study. *J Gastroenterol.* 2008; 43(12): 920-7.
4. Johnson DA, Katz PO. Nocturnal gastroesophageal reflux disease: issues, implications, and management strategies. *Rev Gastroenterol Disord.* 2008 Spring;8(2):98-108.
5. Iwakiri K, Kawami N, Sano H, Tanaka Y, Umezawa M, Kotoyori M, Hoshihara Y, Sakamoto C. Acid and non-acid reflux in Japanese patients with non-erosive reflux disease with persistent reflux symptoms, despite taking a double-dose of proton pump inhibitor: a study using combined pH-impedance monitoring. *J Gastroenterol.* 2009; 44(7): 708-12.
6. Kusunoki H, Kusaka M, Kido S, Yamauchi R, Fujimura Y, Watanabe Y, Kobori M, Miwa H, Tomita T, Kin Y, Hori K, Tano N, Sugimoto K, Nakamura Y, Fujimoto K, Oza N, Matsunobu A, Ono N, Fuyuno S, Kinoshita Y, Adachi K, Yuki M, Fujisawa T, Haruma K. Comparison of the effects of omeprazole and famotidine in treatment of upper abdominal symptoms in patients with reflux esophagitis. *J Gastroenterol.* 2009;44(4):261-70.
7. Ho KY, Kuan A, Zaño F, Goh KL, Mahachai V, Kim DY, Yoon HM. Randomized, parallel, double-blind comparison of the ulcer-healing effects of ilaprazole and omeprazole in the treatment of gastric and duodenal ulcers. *J Gastroenterol.* 2009;44(7):697-707.
8. Nishizawa T, Suzuki H, Hibi T. Quinolone-Based Third-Line Therapy for *Helicobacter pylori* Eradication. *J Clin Biochem Nutr.* 2009 Mar; 44(2): 119-124.
9. Ichikawa H, Yoshida N, Takagi T, Tomatsuri N, Katada K, Isozaki Y, Uchiyama K, Naito Y, Okanoue T, Yoshikawa T. Lansoprazole ameliorates intestinal mucosal damage induced by ischemia-reperfusion in rats. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2004;10(19):2814-7.
10. Kuroda M, Yoshida N, Ichikawa H, Takagi T, Okuda T, Naito Y, Okanoue T, Yoshikawa T. Lansoprazole, a proton pump inhibitor, reduces the severity of indomethacin-induced rat enteritis. *Int J Mol Med.* 2006; 17(1): 89-93.
11. González-Ortiz M, Martínez-Abundis E, Mercado-Sesma AR, Álvarez-Carrillo R. Effect of pantoprazole on insulin secretion in drug-naïve patients with type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract.* 2015;108(1): e11-3.
12. Becker JC, Grosser N, Waltke C, Schulz S, Erdmann K, Domschke W, Schröder H, Pohle T. Beyond gastric acid reduction: proton pump inhibitors induce heme oxygenase-1 in gastric and endothelial cells. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun.* 2006; 345(3):1014-21.
13. Yeo M, Kim DK, Kim YB, Oh TY, Lee JE, Cho SW, Kim HC, Hahm KB. Selective induction of apoptosis with proton pump inhibitor in gastric cancer cells. *Clin Cancer Res.* 2004; 10(24):8687-96.
14. Nakao M, Malfertheiner P. Growth inhibitory and bactericidal activities of lansoprazole compared with those of omeprazole and pantoprazole against *Helicobacter pylori*. *Helicobacter.* 1998; 3(1): 21-7.
15. Koop H, Klein M, Arnold R. Serum gastrin levels during long-term omeprazole treatment. *Aliment Pharmacol Ther.* 1990 Apr;4(2):131-8.
16. Sanders SW, Tolman KG, Greski PA, Jennings DE, Hoyos PA, Page JG. The effects of lansoprazole, a new H⁺, K⁺-ATPase inhibitor, on gastric pH and serum gastrin. *Alimentary pharmacology and therapeutics* 1992; 6 (3): 359-372.
17. Cadiot G, Vissuzaine C, Pospai D, Ruzsniowski P, Potet F, Mignon M. [Effect of prolonged treatment with proton pump inhibitors on serum gastrin levels and the fundus mucosa. Preliminary results]. *Gastroenterol Clin Biol.* 1995 Oct;19(10):811-7.
18. Ligumsky M, Lysy J, Siguencia G, Friedlander Y. Effect of long-term, continuous versus alternate-day omeprazole therapy on serum gastrin in patients treated for reflux esophagitis. *J Clin Gastroenterol.* 2001; 33(1):32-5.
19. Yong-Mei Hu, Qiao Mei, Xin-Hua Xu, Xiang-Peng Hu, Nai-Zhong Hu, and Jian-Ming Xu. Pharmacodynamic and kinetic effect of rabeprazole on serum gastrin level in relation to CYP2C19 polymorphism in Chinese Hans. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2006 Aug 7; 12(29): 4750-4753
20. Sheen E, Triadafilopoulos G. Adverse effects of long-term proton pump inhibitor therapy. *Dig Dis Sci.* 2011; 56(4):931-50.
21. Gregory R, Tracy H. Isolation of two "big gastrins" from Zollinger-ellison tumour tissue. *The Lancet* 1972; 300 (7781): 797-799.
22. Burkitt M, Varro A, Pritchard M. Importance of gastrin in the pathogenesis and treatment of gastric tumors. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2009 Jan 7; 15(1): 1-16.
23. Téllez N, Joanny G, Escoriza J, Vilaseca M, Montanya E. Gastrin Treatment Stimulates β -Cell Regeneration and Improves Glucose Tolerance in 95% Pancreatectomized Rats *Endocrinology* 2011; 152: 2580-2588.
24. Rooman I, Lardon J, Bouwens L. Gastrin stimulates beta-cell neogenesis and increases islet mass from transdifferentiated but not from normal exocrine pancreas tissue. *Diabetes.* 2002; 51(3): 686-90.
25. Bödvarsdóttir TB, Hove KD, Gotfredsen CF, Pridal L, Vaag A, Karlsen AE, JS Petersen. Treatment with a proton pump inhibitor improves glycaemic control in *Psammomys obesus*, a model of type 2 diabetes. *Diabetologia.* 2010; 53(10): 2220-2223.
26. Mefford IN, Wade EU. Proton pump inhibitors as a treatment method for type II diabetes. *Med Hypotheses.* 2009;73(1):29-32.
27. Hove KD, Færch K, Bödvarsdóttir TB, Karlsen AE, Petersen JS, Vaag A. Treatment with a proton pump inhibitor improves glycaemic control in type 2

- diabetic patients - a retrospective analysis. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract.* 2010;90(3): e72-4.
28. Boj-Carceller D, Bocos-Terraz P, Moreno-Vernis M, Sanz-Paris A, Trincado-Aznar P, Albero-Gamboa R. Are proton pump inhibitors a new antidiabetic drug? A cross sectional study. *World J Diabetes.* 2011; 2(12): 217–220.
 29. Crouch MA, Mefford IN, Wade EU. Proton pump inhibitor therapy associated with lower glycosylated hemoglobin levels in type 2 diabetes. *J Am Board Fam Med.* 2012;25(1):50-4.
 30. Singh PK, Hota D, Dutta P, Sachdeva N, Chakrabarti A, Srinivasan A, Singh I, Bhansali A. Pantoprazole improves glycemic control in type 2 diabetes: a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2012;97(11): E2105-8.
 31. Barchetta I, Guglielmi C, Bertocchini L, Calella D, Manfrini S, Secchi C, Pozzilli P, Cavallo MG; IMDIAB group. Therapy with proton pump inhibitors in patients with type 2 diabetes is independently associated with improved glycometabolic control. *Acta Diabetol.* 2015; 52(5): 873-80.
 32. Han N, Oh M, Park SM, Kim YJ, Lee EJ, Kim TK, Kim TN, Kwon MJ, Kim MK, Lee SH, Rhee BD, Park JH. The effect of proton pump inhibitors on glycated hemoglobin levels in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Can J Diabetes.* 2015;39(1):24-8.
 33. Hove KD, Brøns C, Færch K, Lund SS, Petersen JS, Karlsen AE, Rossing P, Rehfeld JF, Vaag A. Effects of 12 weeks' treatment with a proton pump inhibitor on insulin secretion, glucose metabolism and markers of cardiovascular risk in patients with type 2 diabetes: a randomised double-blind prospective placebo-controlled study. *Diabetologia.* 2013;56(1):22-30.
 34. Rau TT, Sonst A, Rogler A, Burnat G, Neumann H, Oeckl K, Neuhuber W, Dimmler A, Faller G, Brzozowski T, Hartmann A, Konturek PC. Gastrin mediated down regulation of ghrelin and its pathophysiological role in atrophic gastritis. *J Physiol Pharmacol.* 2013;64(6):719-25.
 35. Dufresne M, Seva C, Fourmy D. Cholecystokinin and gastrin receptors. *Physiol Rev.* 2006;86(3):805-47.
 36. Mercer LD, Le VQ, Nunan J, Jones NM, Beart PM. Direct visualization of cholecystokinin subtype2 receptors in rat central nervous system using anti-peptide antibodies. *Neurosci Lett.* 2000; 293(3):167-70.
 37. Greenstein RJ, Clain DJ, Straus E, Yalow RS. Distribution, molecular forms, and bioactivity of immunoreactive gastrin in a patient with metastatic gastrinoma. *Am J Gastroenterol.* 1987; 82(9): 886-9.
 38. Banks WA, Audus KL, Davis TP. Permeability of the blood-brain barrier to peptides: an approach to the development of therapeutically useful analogs. *Peptides.* 1992; 13(6): 1289-94.
 39. Danzer M, Jovic M, Samberger C, Painsipp E, Bock E, Pabst M, Crailsheim K, Schicho R, Lippe I, Holzer P. Stomach-brain communication by vagal afferents in response to luminal acid backdiffusion, gastrin, and gastric acid secretion *Am J Physiol Gastrointest Liver Physiol*2004; 286: G403–G411.
 40. Cao Y, Cao X, Liu XM. Expression of cholecystokinin2-receptor in rat and human L cells and the stimulation of glucagon-like peptide-1 secretion by gastrin treatment. *Acta Histochem.* 2015;117(2):205-10.
 41. Suarez-Pinzon W, Power R, Yan Y, Wasserfall C, Atkinson M, Rabinovitch A. Combination Therapy with Glucagon-Like Peptide-1 and Gastrin Restores Normoglycemia in Diabetic NOD Mice. *Diabetes.* 2008; 57(12): 3281–3288.
 42. Lavine JA, Attie AD. Gastrointestinal hormones and the regulation of β -cell mass. *Ann N Y Acad Sci.* 2010; 1212:41-58.
 43. Fosgerau K, Jessen L, Lind Tolborg J, Østerlund T, Schæffer Larsen K, Rolsted K, Brorson M, Jelsing J, Skovlund Ryge Neerup T. The novel GLP-1-gastrin dual agonist, ZP3022, increases β -cell mass and prevents diabetes in db/db mice. *Diabetes Obes Metab.* 2013; 15(1): 62-71.
 44. Suarez-Pinzon WL, Rabinovitch A. Combination therapy with a dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitor and a proton pump inhibitor induces β -cell neogenesis from adult human pancreatic duct cells implanted in immunodeficient mice. *Cell Transplant.* 2011; 20(9): 1343-9.
 45. Hao S, Sun J, Tian X, Sun X, Zhang Z, Gao Y. Lansoprazole enhances the antidiabetic effect of sitagliptin in mice with diet-induced obesity and healthy human subjects. *J Pharm Pharmacol.* 2014; 66(8):1133-9.
 46. Stocker R, Yamamoto Y, McDonagh AF, Glazer AN, Ames BN. Bilirubin is an antioxidant of possible physiological importance. *Science.* 1987; 235(4792):1043-6.
 47. Yesilkaya A, Altinayak R, Korgun D. The antioxidant effect of free bilirubin on cumenehydroperoxide treated human leukocytes. *General Pharmacology: The Vascular System.* 2000; 35 (1): 17–20.
 48. Otterbein LE, Bach FH, Alam J, Soares M, Tao Lu H, Wysk M, Davis RJ, Flavell RA, Choi AM. Carbon monoxide has anti-inflammatory effects involving the mitogen-activated protein kinase pathway. *Nat Med.* 2000; 6(4):422-8.
 49. Constantin M, Choi A, Cloonan S, Ryter S. Therapeutic Potential of Heme Oxygenase-1/Carbon Monoxide in Lung Disease. *International Journal of Hypertension.* 2012; 2012 (2012), Article ID 859235, 19 pages.
 50. Blandizzi C, Natale G, Gherardi G, Lazzeri G, Marveggio C, Colucci R, Carignani D, Del Tacca M. Acid-independent gastroprotective effects of lansoprazole in experimental mucosal injury. *Dig Dis Sci.* 1999; 44(10): 2039-50.
 51. Pastoris OI, Verri M, Boschi F, Kastsuchenka O, Balestra B, Pace F, Tonini M, Natale G. Effects of esomeprazole on glutathione levels and mitochondrial oxidative phosphorylation in the gastric mucosa of

- rats treated with indomethacin. *Naunyn Schmiedebergs Arch Pharmacol.* 2008; 378(4): 421-9.
52. Biswas K, Bandyopadhyay U, Chattopadhyay I, Varadaraj A, Ali E, Banerjee RK.. A novel antioxidant and antiapoptotic role of omeprazole to block gastric ulcer through scavenging of hydroxyl radical. *J Biol Chem.* 2003; 278(13):10993-1001.
 53. Blandizzi C, Fornai M, Colucci R, Natale G, Lubrano V, Vassalle C, Antonioli L, Lazzeri G, Del Tacca M. Lansoprazole prevents experimental gastric injury induced by non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs through a reduction of mucosal oxidative damage. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2005;11(26):4052-60.
 54. Simon WA, Sturm E, Hartmann HJ, Weser U. Hydroxyl radical scavenging reactivity of proton pump inhibitors. *Biochem Pharmacol.* 2006;71(9):1337-41.
 55. Weiss SJ. Oxygen, ischemia and inflammation. *Acta Physiol Scand Suppl.* 1986; 548:9-37.
 56. Lapenna D, de Gioia S, Ciofani G, Festi D, Cucurullo F. Antioxidant properties of omeprazole. *FEBS Letters* 1996; 382 (1–2): 189-192.
 57. Igarashi K, Sun J.. The heme-Bach1 pathway in the regulation of oxidative stress response and erythroid differentiation. *Antioxid Redox Signal.* 2006; 8(1-2):107-18.
 58. Lim HJ, Lee KS, Lee S, Park JH, Choi HE, Go SH, Kwak HJ, Park HY. 15d-PGJ2 stimulates HO-1 expression through p38 MAP kinase and Nrf-2 pathway in rat vascular smooth muscle cells. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol.* 2007; 223(1):20-7.
 59. Ferrándiz ML, Devesa I. Inducers of heme oxygenase-1. *Curr Pharm Des.* 2008; 14(5): 473-86.
 60. Morse D, Lin L, Choi AM, Ryter SW. Heme oxygenase-1, a critical arbitrator of cell death pathways in lung injury and disease. *Free Radic Biol Med.* 2009;47(1):1-12.
 61. Takagi T, Naito Y, Okada H, Ishii T, Mizushima K, Akagiri S, Adachi S, Handa O, Kokura S, Ichikawa H, Itoh K, Yamamoto M, Matsui H, Yoshikawa T. Lansoprazole, a proton pump inhibitor, mediates anti-inflammatory effect in gastric mucosal cells through the induction of heme oxygenase-1 via activation of NF-E2-related factor 2 and oxidation of kelch-like ECH-associating protein 1. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther.* 2009;331(1):255-64.
 62. Tanigawa T, Watanabe T, Higuchi K, Machida H, Okazaki H, Yamagami H, Watanabe K, Tominaga K, Fujiwara Y, Oshitani N, Arakawa T. Lansoprazole, a Proton Pump Inhibitor, Suppresses Production of Tumor Necrosis Factor-alpha and Interleukin-1beta Induced by Lipopolysaccharide and Helicobacter Pylori Bacterial Components in Human Monocytic Cells via Inhibition of Activation of Nuclear Factor-kappaB and Extracellular Signal-Regulated Kinase. *J Clin Biochem Nutr.* 2009;45(1):86-92.
 63. Isomoto H, Nishi Y, Wang A, Takeshima F, Omagari K, Mizuta Y, Shikuwa S, Murata I, Kohno S. Mucosal concentrations of proinflammatory cytokines and chemokines at gastric cardia: implication of Helicobacter pylori infection and gastroesophageal reflux. *Am J Gastroenterol.* 2004;99(6):1063-8.
 64. Yoshida N, Uchiyama K, Kuroda M, Sakuma K, Kokura S, Ichikawa H, Naito Y, Takemura T, Yoshikawa T, Okanoue T. Interleukin-8 expression in the esophageal mucosa of patients with gastroesophageal reflux disease. *Scand J Gastroenterol.* 2004; 39(9): 816-22.
 65. Isomoto H, Nishi Y, Kanazawa Y, Shikuwa S, Mizuta Y, Inoue K, Kohno S. Immune and Inflammatory Responses in GERD and Lansoprazole. *J Clin Biochem Nutr.* 2007; 41(2): 84–91.
 66. Ohara T, Morishita T, Suzuki H, Masaoka T, Nishizawa T, Hibi T. Investigation of the possibility of human-beta defensin 2 (hBD2) as a molecular marker of gastric mucosal inflammation. *Hepatogastroenterology.* 2005; 52(65):1320-4.
 67. Higuchi K, Yoda Y, Amagase K, Kato S, Tokioka S, Murano M, Takeuchi K, Umegaki E. Prevention of NSAID-Induced Small Intestinal Mucosal Injury: Prophylactic Potential of Lansoprazole. *J Clin Biochem Nutr.* 2009; 45(2): 125–130.
 68. Hendriks HJ, van Kreel B, Forget PP. Effects of therapy with lansoprazole on intestinal permeability and inflammation in young cystic fibrosis patients. *J Pediatr Gastroenterol Nutr.* 2001;33(3):260-5.
 69. Wallace JL, Arfors KE, McKnight GW. A monoclonal antibody against the CD18 leukocyte adhesion molecule prevents indomethacin-induced gastric damage in the rabbit. *Gastroenterology.* 1991;100(4):878-83.
 70. Yoshida N, Granger DN, Evans DJ Jr, Evans DG, Graham DY, Anderson DC, Wolf RE, Kvietys PR. Mechanisms involved in Helicobacter pylori-induced inflammation. *Gastroenterology.* 1993;105(5):1431-40.
 71. Yoshida N1, Takemura T, Granger DN, Anderson DC, Wolf RE, McIntire LV, Kvietys PR. Molecular determinants of aspirin-induced neutrophil adherence to endothelial cells. *Gastroenterology.* 1993;105(3):715-24.
 72. Takemura T1, Granger DN, Evans DJ Jr, Evans DG, Graham DY, Anderson DC, Wolf RE, Cepinskas G, Kvietys PR. Extract of Helicobacter pylori induces neutrophils to injure endothelial cells and contains antielastase activity. *Gastroenterology.* 1996;110(1):21-9.
 73. Yoshida N, Yoshikawa T, Nakamura Y, Arai M, Matsuyama K, Inuma S, Yagi N, Naito Y, Miyasaka M, Kondo M. Role of neutrophil-mediated inflammation in aspirin-induced gastric mucosal injury. *Dig Dis Sci.* 1995;40(11):2300-4.
 74. Tonnesen MG. Neutrophil-endothelial cell interactions: mechanisms of neutrophil adherence to vascular endothelium. *J Invest Dermatol.* 1989; 93(Suppl): 53S-58S.
 75. Springer TA. Adhesion receptors of the immune system. *Nature.* 1990; 346(6283):425-34.
 76. Smith CW, Marlin SD, Rothlein R, Toman C, Anderson DC. Cooperative interactions of LFA-1 and

- Mac-1 with intercellular adhesion molecule-1 in facilitating adherence and transendothelial migration of human neutrophils in vitro. *J Clin Invest.* 1989; 83(6):2008-17.
77. Carlos TM, Harlan JM. Membrane proteins involved in phagocyte adherence to endothelium. *Immunol Rev.* 1990; 114:5-28.
 78. Carlos T, Kovach N, Rosa S, Newrnan B, Wayner E, Benjamin C, Osborn L, Lobb R, Harlan J. Human Monocytes Bind to Two Cytokine-Induced Adhesive Ligands on Cultured Human Endothelial Cells: Endothelial-Leukocyte Adhesion Molecule-1 and Vascular Cell Adhesion Molecule-1. *Blood* 1991; 77 (10): 2266-2271.
 79. Yoshida N, Yoshikawa T, Tanaka Y, Fujita N, Kassai K, Naito Y, Kondo M. A new mechanism for anti-inflammatory actions of proton pump inhibitors--inhibitory effects on neutrophil-endothelial cell interactions. *Aliment Pharmacol Ther.* 2000;14 (1):74-81.
 80. Wandall JH. Effects of omeprazole on neutrophil chemotaxis, super oxide production, degranulation, and translocation of cytochrome b-245. *Gut.* 1992; 33(5): 617-21.
 81. Hou J, Baichwal V, Cao Z. Regulatory elements and transcription factors controlling basal and cytokine-induced expression of the gene encoding intercellular adhesion molecule 1. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 1994; 91(24):11641-5.
 82. Martins de Oliveira R, Antunes E, Pedrazzoli J Jr, Gambero A. The inhibitory effects of H⁺ K⁺ ATPase inhibitors on human neutrophils in vitro: restoration by a K⁺ ionophore. *Inflamm Res.* 2007; 56(3):105-11.
 83. Agastya G, West BC, Callahan JM. Omeprazole inhibits phagocytosis and acidification of phagolysosomes of normal human neutrophils in vitro. *Immunopharmacol Immunotoxicol.* 2000; 22(2):357-72.
 84. Céline Lafourcade, Komla Sobo,1 Sylvie Kieffer-Jaquinod,2 Jérôme Garin,2 and F. Gisou van der Goot,. Regulation of the V-ATPase along the Endocytic Pathway Occurs through Reversible Subunit Association and Membrane Localization. *PLoS ONE.* 2008; 3(7): e2758
 85. Luciani F, Spada M, De Milito A, Molinari A, Rivoltini L, Montinaro A, Marra M, Lugini L, Logozzi M, Lozupone F, Federici C, Iessi E, Parmiani G, Arancia G, Belardelli F, Fais S. Effect of proton pump inhibitor pretreatment on resistance of solid tumors to cytotoxic drugs. *J Natl Cancer Inst.* 2004;96(22):1702-13.
 86. Harada M, Shakado S, Sakisaka S, Tamaki S, Ohishi M, Sasatomi K, Koga H, Sata M, Tanikawa K. Bafilomycin A1, a specific inhibitor of V-type H⁺-ATPases, inhibits the acidification of endocytic structures and inhibits horseradish peroxidase uptake in isolated rat sinusoidal endothelial cells. *Liver.* 1997; 17(5): 244-50.
 87. Handa O, Yoshida N, Fujita N, Tanaka Y, Ueda M, Takagi T, Kokura S, Naito Y, Okanoue T, Yoshikawa T. Molecular mechanisms involved in anti-inflammatory effects of proton pump inhibitors. *Inflamm Res.* 2006; 55(11): 476-80.
 88. Sasaki T, Yamaya M, Yasuda H, Inoue D, Yamada M, Kubo H, Nishimura H, Sasaki H. The proton pump inhibitor lansoprazole inhibits rhinovirus infection in cultured human tracheal epithelial cells. *Eur J Pharmacol.* 2005 Feb 21;509(2-3):201-10.
 89. Jung HC, Kim JM, Song IS, Kim CY. Helicobacter pylori induces an array of pro-inflammatory cytokines in human gastric epithelial cells: quantification of mRNA for interleukin-8, -1 alpha/beta, granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor, monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 and tumour necrosis factor-alpha. *J Gastroenterol Hepatol.* 1997; 12(7): 473-80.
 90. Hatz RA, Rieder G, Stolte M, Bayerdörffer E, Meimarakis G, Schildberg FW, Enders G. Pattern of adhesion molecule expression on vascular endothelium in Helicobacter pylori-associated antral gastritis. *Gastroenterology.* 1997;112(6):1908-19.
 91. Ohara T, Arakawa T. Lansoprazole decreases peripheral blood monocytes and intercellular adhesion molecule-1-positive mononuclear cells. *Dig Dis Sci.* 1999;44(8):1710-5.
 92. Smith W B, Gamble J R, Clark-Lewis I, Vadas M A. Interleukin-8 induces neutrophil transendothelial migration. *Immunology.* 1991; 72(1): 65-72.
 93. Itoh K, Wakabayashi N, Katoh Y, Ishii T, Igarashi K, Engel JD, Yamamoto M.. Keap1 represses nuclear activation of antioxidant responsive elements by Nrf2 through binding to the amino-terminal Neh2 domain. *Genes Dev.* 1999;13(1):76-86.
 94. Alam J, Stewart D, Touchard C, Boinapally S, Choi A, Cook J. Nrf2, a Cap'n'Collar Transcription Factor, Regulates Induction of the Heme Oxygenase-1 Gene. *The Journal of Biological chemistry* 1999; 274: 26071-26078.
 95. Ishii T, Itoh K, Takahashi S, Sato H, Yanagawa T, Katoh Y, Bannai S, Yamamoto M.. Transcription factor Nrf2 coordinately regulates a group of oxidative stress-inducible genes in macrophages. *J Biol Chem.* 2000; 275(21):16023-9.
 96. Itoh K, Wakabayashi N, Katoh Y, Ishii T, O'Connor T, Yamamoto M. Keap1 regulates both cytoplasmic-nuclear shuttling and degradation of Nrf2 in response to electrophiles. *Genes Cells.* 2003; 8(4): 379-91.
 97. Ryter SW, Choi AM. Heme oxygenase-1: redox regulation of a stress protein in lung and cell culture models. *Antioxid Redox Signal.* 2005; 7(1-2): 80-91.
 98. Naito Y, Takagi T, Yoshikawa T. Lansoprazole, a Proton Pump Inhibitor, to Reduce Gastrointestinal Inflammation via Heme Oxygenase-1 Induction. *Mol Cell Pharmacol* 2010; 2(2): 53-60.
 99. Nakamura M, Matsui H, Serizawa H, Tsuchimoto K. Lansoprazole Novel Effector Sites Revealed by Autoradiography: Relation to Helicobacter pylori, Colon, Esophagus and Others. *J Clin Biochem Nutr.* 2007;41(3):154-9.
 100. Schwer CI, Guerrero AM, Humar M, Roesslein M, Goebel U, Stoll P, Geiger KK, Pannen BH, Hoetzel A,

- Schmidt R. Heme oxygenase-1 inhibits the proliferation of pancreatic stellate cells by repression of the extracellular signal-regulated kinase1/2 pathway. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther.* 2008; 327(3): 863-71.
101. Ngo P, Furuta GT, Antonioli DA, Fox VL. Eosinophils in the esophagus--peptic or allergic eosinophilic esophagitis? Case series of three patients with esophageal eosinophilia. *Am J Gastroenterol.* 2006;101(7):1666-70.
102. Spechler SJ, Genta RM, Souza RF. Thoughts on the complex relationship between gastroesophageal reflux disease and eosinophilic esophagitis. *Am J Gastroenterol.* 2007; 102(6): 1301-6.
103. Aceves SS, Furuta GT, Spechler SJ. Integrated approach to treatment of children and adults with eosinophilic esophagitis. *Gastrointest Endosc Clin N Am.* 2008;18(1):195-217.
104. Bohm M, Richter JE. Treatment of eosinophilic esophagitis: overview, current limitations, and future direction. *Am J Gastroenterol.* 2008;103(10):2635-44.
105. Namazi MR1, Jowkar F. A succinct review of the general and immunological pharmacologic effects of proton pump inhibitors. *J Clin Pharm Ther.* 2008; 33(3): 215-7.
106. Pullamsetti SS, Savai R, Dumitrascu R, Dahal BK, Wilhelm J, Konigshoff M, et al. The role of dimethylarginine dimethylaminohydrolase in idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis. *Sci Transl Med.* 2011; 3: 87ra53.
107. Genovese T, Cuzzocrea S, Di Paola R, Failla M, Mazzon E, Sortino MA, et al. Inhibition or knock out of inducible nitric oxide synthase result in resistance to bleomycin-induced lung injury. *Respir Res.* 2005; 6: 58.
108. Ghebremariam Y, Cooke J, Gerhart W, Griego C, Brower J, Doyle-Eisele M, Moeller B, Zhou Q, Ho L, de Andrade J, Raghu G, Peterson L, Rivera A, Rosen G. Pleiotropic effect of the proton pump inhibitor esomeprazole leading to suppression of lung inflammation and fibrosis *J Transl Med.* 2015; 13: 249.
109. Izumi H, Torigoe T, Ishiguchi H, Uramoto H, Yoshida Y, Tanabe M, Ise T, Murakami T, Yoshida T, Nomoto M, Kohno K. Cellular pH regulators: potentially promising molecular targets for cancer chemotherapy. *Cancer Treat Rev.* 2003; 29(6): 541-9.
110. Nishi T, Forgac M. The vacuolar (H⁺)-ATPases--nature's most versatile proton pumps. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol.* 2002; 3: 94-103.
111. Forgac M., Vacuolar ATPases: rotary proton pumps in physiology and pathophysiology. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol.* 2007; 8: 917-29
112. Toei M, Saum R, Forgac M. Regulation and isoform function of the V-ATPases. *Biochemistry.* 2010; 49: 4715-23
113. Fais S, De Milito A, You H, Qin W. Targeting vacuolar H⁺-ATPases as a new strategy against cancer. *Cancer Res.* 2007; 67: 10627-30.
114. Martínez-Zaguilán R, Raghunand N, Lynch RM, Bellamy W, Martinez GM, Rojas B, Smith D, Dalton WS, Gillies RJ. pH and drug resistance. I. Functional expression of plasmalemmal V-type H⁺-ATPase in drug-resistant human breast carcinoma cell lines. *Biochem Pharmacol.* 1999; 57: 1037-46.
115. Luciani F, Spada M, De Milito A, Molinari A, Rivoltini L, Montinaro A, Marra M, Lugini L, Logozzi M, Lozupone F, Federici C, Iessi E, Parmiani G, Arancia G, Belardelli F, Fais S. Effect of proton pump inhibitor pretreatment on resistance of solid tumors to cytotoxic drugs. *J Natl Cancer Inst.* 2004; 96: 1702-13.
116. Lu X, Qin W, Li J, Tan N, Pan D, Zhang H, Xie L, Yao G, Shu H, Yao M, Wan D, Gu J, Yang S. The growth and metastasis of human hepatocellular carcinoma xenografts are inhibited by small interfering RNA targeting to the subunit ATP6L of proton pump. *Cancer Res.* 2005; 65: 6843-9.
117. Robey IF, Baggett BK, Kirkpatrick ND, Roe DJ, Dosescu J, Sloane BF, Hashim AI, Morse DL, Raghunand N, Gatenby RA, Gillies RJ. Bicarbonate increases tumor pH and inhibits spontaneous metastases. *Cancer Res.* 2009; 69:2260-8.
118. Muench SP, Trinick J, Harrison MA. Structural divergence of the rotary ATPases. *Q Rev Biophys.* 2011; 44: 311-56
119. Subarsky P, Hill RP. The hypoxic tumour microenvironment and metastatic progression. *Clin Exp Metastasis.* 2003; 20: 237-50
120. Gillies RJ, Robey I, Gatenby RA. Causes and consequences of increased glucose metabolism of cancers. *J Nucl Med.* 2008; 49: 24S-42S
121. Trédan O, Galmarini CM, Patel K, Tannock IF. Drug resistance and the solid tumor microenvironment. *J Natl Cancer Inst.* 2007; 99: 1441-54.
122. Chiche J, Brahimi-Horn MC, Pouyssegur J. Tumour hypoxia induces a metabolic shift causing acidosis: a common feature in cancer. *J Cell Mol Med.* 2010; 14: 771-94.
123. Torigoe T, Izumi H, Ishiguchi H, Uramoto H, Murakami T, Ise T, Yoshida Y, Tanabe M, Nomoto M, Itoh H, Kohno K. Enhanced expression of the human vacuolar H⁺-ATPase c subunit gene (ATP6L) in response to anticancer agents. *J Biol Chem.* 2002; 277: 36534-43
124. Morimura T, Fujita K, Akita M, Nagashima M, Satomi A. The proton pump inhibitor inhibits cell growth and induces apoptosis in human hepatoblastoma. *Pediatr Surg Int.* 2008; 24:1087-94.
125. McHenry P, Wang WL, Devitt E, Kluesner N, Davisson VJ, McKee E, Schweitzer D, Helquist P, Tenniswood M. Iejimalides A and B inhibit lysosomal vacuolar H⁺-ATPase (V-ATPase) activity and induce S-phase arrest and apoptosis in MCF-7 cells. *J Cell Biochem.* 2010; 109: 634-42.
126. Nakashima S, Hiraku Y, Tada-Oikawa S, Hishita T, Gabazza EC, Tamaki S, Imoto I, Adachi Y, Kawanishi S (2003) Vacuolar H⁺-ATPase inhibitor induces apoptosis via lysosomal dysfunction in the human

- gastric cancer cell line MKN-1. *J Biochem* 134, 359-364.
127. Nishihara T, Akifusa S, Koseki T, Kato S, Muro M, Hanada N. Specific inhibitors of vacuolar type H(+)-ATPases induce apoptotic cell death. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun*. 1995; 212: 255-62.
 128. De Milito A, Iessi E, Logozzi M, Lozupone F, Spada M, Marino ML, Federici C, Perdicchio M, Matarrese P, Lugini L, Nilsson A, Fais S. Proton pump inhibitors induce apoptosis of human B-cell tumors through a caspase-independent mechanism involving reactive oxygen species. *Cancer Res*. 2007; 67: 5408-17.
 129. Sasazawa Y, Futamura Y, Tashiro E, Imoto M. Vacuolar H⁺-ATPase inhibitors overcome Bcl-xL-mediated chemoresistance through restoration of a caspase-independent apoptotic pathway. *Cancer Sci*. 2009; 100: 1460-7.
 130. Ishisaki A, Hashimoto S, Amagasa T, Nishihara T. Caspase-3 activation during the process of apoptosis induced by a vacuolar type H (+)-ATPase inhibitor. *Biol Cell*. 1999; 91: 507-13.
 131. O'Callaghan KM, Ayllon V, O'Keefe J, Wang Y, Cox OT, Loughran G, Forgac M, O'Connor R. Heme-binding protein HRG-1 is induced by insulin-like growth factor I and associates with the vacuolar H⁺-ATPase to control endosomal pH and receptor trafficking. *J Biol Chem*. 2010; 285: 381-91.
 132. Fortini ME, Bilder D. Endocytic regulation of Notch signaling. *Curr Opin Genet Dev*. 2009; 19: 323-8.
 133. Vaccari T, Duchi S, Cortese K, Tacchetti C, Bilder D. The vacuolar ATPase is required for physiological as well as pathological activation of the Notch receptor. *Development*. 2010; 137: 1825-32.
 134. Cruciat CM, Ohkawara B, Acebron SP, Karaulanov E, Reinhard C, Ingelfinger D, Boutros M, Niehrs C. Requirement of prorenin receptor and vacuolar H⁺-ATPase-mediated acidification for Wnt signaling. *Science*. 2010; 327: 459-63.
 135. Buechling T, Bartscherer K, Ohkawara B, Chaudhary V, Spirohn K, Niehrs C, Boutros M. Wnt/Frizzled signaling requires dPRR, the Drosophila homolog of the prorenin receptor. *Curr Biol*. 2010; 20: 1263-8.
 136. Lucio M, Todd G, Barbara O. Notch signaling in cancer. *Current Molecular Medicine* 2006; 6: 905-918.
 137. Roy M, Pear WS, Aster JC. The multifaceted role of Notch in cancer. *Curr Opin Genet Dev*. 2007; 17: 52-9.
 138. Nishisho T, Hata K, Nakanishi M, Morita Y, Sun-Wada GH, Wada Y, Yasui N, Yoneda T. The $\alpha 3$ isoform vacuolar type H⁺-ATPase promotes distant metastasis in the mouse B16 melanoma cells. *Mol Cancer Res*. 2011; 9: 845-55.
 139. Chung C, Mader CC, Schmitz JC, Atladottir J, Fitchev P, Cornwell ML, Koleske AJ, Crawford SE, Gorelick F. The vacuolar-ATPase modulates matrix metalloproteinase isoforms in human pancreatic cancer. *Lab Invest*. 2011; 91: 732-43.
 140. Sennoune SR, Bakunts K, Martínez GM, Chua-Tuan JL, Kebir Y, Attaya MN, Martínez-Zaguilán R. Vacuolar H⁺-ATPase in human breast cancer cells with distinct metastatic potential: distribution and functional activity. *Am J Physiol Cell Physiol*. 2004; 286: C1443-52.
 141. Hinton A, Sennoune SR, Bond S, Fang M, Reuveni M, Sahagian GG, Jay D, Martinez-Zaguilan R, Forgac M. Function of a subunit isoforms of the V-ATPase in pH homeostasis and in vitro invasion of MDA-MB231 human breast cancer cells. *J Biol Chem*. 2009; 284: 16400-8.
 142. Joyce JA, Hanahan D. Multiple roles for cysteine cathepsins in cancer. *Cell Cycle*. 2004; 3: 1516-619.
 143. Gocheva V, Joyce JA. Cysteine cathepsins and the cutting edge of cancer invasion. *Cell Cycle*. 2007; 6: 60-4.
 144. Martínez-Zaguilán R, Seftor EA, Seftor RE, Chu YW, Gillies RJ, Hendrix MJ. Acidic pH enhances the invasive behavior of human melanoma cells. *N Clin Exp Metastasis*. 1996; 14: 176-86.
 145. De Milito A, Fais S. Tumor acidity, chemoresistance and proton pump inhibitors. *Future Oncol*. 200; 1: 779-86.
 146. Luciani F, Spada M, De Milito A, Molinari A, Rivoltini L, Montinaro A, Marra M, Lugini L, Logozzi M, Lozupone F, Federici C, Iessi E, Parmiani G, Arancia G, Belardelli F, Fais S. Effect of proton pump inhibitor pretreatment on resistance of solid tumors to cytotoxic drugs. *J Natl Cancer Inst*. 2004; 96: 1702-13.
 147. Hersey P, Watts RN, Zhang XD, Hackett J. Metabolic approaches to treatment of melanoma. *Clin Cancer Res*. 2009; 15: 6490-4.
 148. Marino ML, Fais S, Djavaheri-Mergny M, Villa A, Meschini S, Lozupone F, Venturi G, Mina PD, Patingre S, Rivoltini L, Codogno P, DeMilito A. Proton pump inhibition induces autophagy as a survival mechanism following oxidative stress in human melanoma cells. *Cell Death Dis*. 2010; 1: e87.
 149. Verdu E, Viani F, Armstrong D, Fraser R, Siegrist HH, Pignatelli B, Idström JP, Cederberg C, Blum AL, Fried M. Effect of omeprazole on intragastric bacterial counts, nitrates, nitrites, and N-nitroso compounds. *Gut*. 1994; 35(4): 455-460.
 150. Vesper BJ, Jawdi A, Altman KW, Haines GK 3rd, Tao L, Radosevich JA. The effect of proton pump inhibitors on the human microbiota. *Curr Drug Metab*. 2009; 10(1):84-9.
 151. Monk BC, Mason AB, Abramochkin G, Haber JE, Seto-Young D, Perlin DS. The yeast plasma membrane proton pumping ATPase is a viable antifungal target. I. Effects of the cysteine-modifying reagent omeprazole. *Biochim Biophys Acta*. 1995; 1239(1):81-90.
 152. Rybniker J. lansoprazole is an antituberculous prodrug targeting cytochrome bc 1. *Nature communications* 2015; 7659.